

An Overview of SDN Control of Multi-Band over SDM Optical Networks with Physical Layer Impairments [Invited]

RAMON CASELLAS,^{1,*} RICARDO MARTINEZ,¹ RICARD VILALTA,¹ RAUL MUÑOZ¹

¹CTTC-CERCA, Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss n7 08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

*Corresponding author: ramon.casellas@cttc.es

Received XX Month XXXX; revised XX Month, XXXX; accepted XX Month XXXX; posted XX Month XXXX (Doc. ID XXXXX); published XX Month XXXX

This paper, an extended version of a tutorial presentation given at OFC'24, aims at providing an overview the key aspects in the design and development of control plane for Multi-Band over Spatial Division Multiplexing optical networks following Software Defined Networking principles. The tutorial will address system design considerations such as the systematic use of data modelling model driven development, will detail selected, industry adopted North Bound and South Bound Interfaces for full and partially disaggregated networks and will introduce some advanced considerations such as accounting for Physical Layer Impairments, externalizing path computation and path validation functions or the multi-level control when considering the management of network media channels over dynamically switched spatial channels. We show a prototype of an SDN controller with multi-granular nodes combining flexi-grid DWDM switching over SDM/core switching including Trasport API extensions for the new protocol layer qualifier.

1. INTRODUCTION

Given the relative maturity of the optical technology, a significant effort has been made to define generic use cases, requirements and frameworks for the control of optical networks adopting Software Defined Networking (SDN) principles [1], and to subsequently extend and produce open and standard data models. Until recently, SDN frameworks and data models have assumed the usage of the C band due to its low attenuation and properties of EDFA amplifiers. However, the increase in traffic and the need for additional capacity [2] justifies the usage of additional optical bands -- often referred to as multiband (MB) or wide-band networking -- as a first step and, in the long term, exploiting the capacity increase provided by spatial domain multiplexing (SDM).

Despite a significant adoption of SDN for the configuration and control of optical networks in the metro/aggregation and core domains, there is a continuous development driven by new or improved technologies at the data plane, to efficiently exploit the increasing programmability and to ensure an efficient and optimal usage of resources with satisfactory quality of transmission with increasing data rates. The adoption of both MB as well as SDM raises new challenges and requirements to the control plane: it is no longer possible to assume neither homogeneous devices nor simple models for transmission and signal propagation nor a single frequency range with quasi-uniform behavior for all channels within the band.

Further development of physical layer impairment (PLI) models, which became necessary with the "beyond 100G" data rates and the adoption of coherent technologies, is critical. The main function of the SDN control plane is to enable the dynamic provisioning with recovery of data services enabling certain automation, so extending SDN for multiband implies accounting for a (potentially) variable number of arbitrary bands, their effects and constraints and, similarly, extending it for SDM requires to carefully consider the implications on network control of having parallel links (SDM lanes) as well as crosstalk and

related effects between such parallel lanes, which has, until now, not been modelled from a control plane perspective. In both cases, accounting for heterogenous composition of devices is also necessary.

This paper is an extension of the OFC tutorial [3]. Its purpose is to provide an overview of the evolution of the control plane design and challenges to support Multiband over SDM (MBoSDM). The paper is structured as follows: in this introductory section, we provide a short overview of optical technologies for capacity scaling and basic ITU-T flexi-grid terminology. Section 2 provides a recap of the SDN framework, based on the adoption of model driven development and open and standard data models as well as architectural, algorithmic and modelling challenges. Section 3 further elaborates on ongoing data modelling affecting control plane constructs, devices and networks. Section 4 addresses the joint control of multi-band flexi-grid networks addressing SDM either as parallel bundles of fibers (BoF) or as multi-core fibers (MCF), relying on the so called multi granular optical nodes (MGON) [4]. Section 5 describes a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) of a single SDN control plane instance controlling an optical network with dual switching capabilities and Section 6 concludes the paper.

A. Optical Transport Networks and Technologies for Capacity Scaling

A key enabler technology for sustained capacity scaling is multi-band transmission, which offers increased capacity in standard single mode fibers (SSMF) by exploiting the S-, E-, O-, and U-bands in addition to C- and/or the commercially available C+L-bands. MB maximizes the use of the currently deployed network infrastructure, with reduced CapEx [5]. Similarly, according to the estimations derived from traffic analysis of [6], regional and national nodes should efficiently manage the aggregated traffic, ranging from a few Tb/s in the short term, ten Tb/s in the medium term, and potentially reaching up to a hundred Tb/s in the long term. Other drivers for the adoption of multiband are capacity scaling, the deployment of optical links in support of data center interconnects, cloud storage/computing and on-demand media

Fig.1. Concepts of Optical Tributary Signal (OTSi) and Media Channel (MC) and OMS/OTS Media Channel Groups (MCG)

consumption, notably when reusing the fiber plant is a key cost factor. The diversity in performance characteristics across different frequency bands provides a strategic advantage as transmission can be flexibly adapted to the specific user needs. However, MB transmission also introduces new challenges such as nonlinear effects (i.e., stimulated Raman scattering, SRS) that must be considered within the system design. Specifically, a power transfer between wavelengths with specific spacing occurs because of the interplay of wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) channels across the various bands [7-8]. Finally, different optical amplifiers, filters, modulators, detectors, and lasers should be included according to the operating band. In general, adopting technologies tailored for specific bands, beyond the traditional C-band, are often accompanied by higher implementation costs [9].

In the medium and long term, solutions will combine wide band and space division multiplexing. The adoption of the technology is gradual, from point-to-point systems focusing on transmission aspects and later addressing switching by means of specialized devices. Introducing SDM switching (either as fiber switching or core/mode switching and variations thereof) enables the "optical bypass", enabling *spatial channels and cross-connects*.

Having several layers does not necessarily mean better performance. An MB over SDM network will have lower blocking rate if the SDM links are always terminated (no switching) and switching happens at the higher WDM layer, allowing a any-to -any switching. Optical bypass becomes of interest in terms of cost efficiency, e.g., when there are specific traffic patterns that favor grooming (multiplexing several high level connections into a low level connection) without resource waste and to reduce node internal architecture and cost or when a single (or small number of) client signal(s) may occupy the entire available spectrum of either a conventional SSMF or one core in a few-mode MCF.

In this context, control plane design deals with the overall question on how to support dynamic provisioning and network automation, identifying initial requirements and proposed extensions.

B. Flexi-Grid reference network for Control and Management

Before moving into the specifics of the control plane, it is needed to define a reference network and introduce a (simplified) key terminology, with the help of Fig.1. An Optical Tributary Signal (OTSi) [10] is defined as an "optical signal that is placed within a network media channel for transport across the optical network (...) and may consist of a single modulated optical carrier or a group of modulated optical carriers or subcarriers.". This corresponds to the superseded "optical channel or OCh. The OTSi is unidirectional in nature and is typically characterized by its modulation format, baud rate, etc. A straightforward extension is the OTSi group (OTSiG) [11] defined as a "set of optical tributary signals (OTSi) that supports a single digital client". Consequently, there is a degree of flexibility in how a digital

signal (e.g. 400 Gb/s) can be modulated in the optical domain, i.e., in terms of single or group of OTSi using single or multicarrier modulation formats. Usually, there is a trade-off in terms of reach/robustness, used spectrum and efficiency. In any case, for a given OTSiG, it is defined that the different components of the OTSi are (i) co-routed over same fibers and (ii) transmitted ensuring a controlled differential delay. Finally, a transceiver [12] commonly corresponds to a Tx/Rx pair and terminates a single OTSi where multiple transceivers can be grouped in a transponder.

From the resource perspective, a Media Channel (MC) [11] is defined as a media (as in optical transmission media) association that represents both the topology (i.e., the path) and the resource (i.e., frequency slot or spectrum range) that it occupies". In simple terms, it can be understood as an effective (resulting from a concatenation of filters) frequency range in an optical media topological construct such a fiber or concatenation of fibers and filters. More specifically, a Media Channel Supports zero or more OTSi; a Network Media Channel (NMC, also referred to an end-to-end media channel) is then defined between transceiver media ports (zero or one OTSi) and roughly corresponds to the Optical Channel Carrier (OCC) in fixed grid networks. Finally, a media Channel Group (MCG) [11] a unidirectional point-to-point management/control abstraction that represents a set of one or more media channels that are co-routed. A media channel group is bounded by a pair of media ports. Of specific relevance in a multidomain context are the Optical Transmission Section (OTS) Media Channel Group (MCG), which from a management perspective is a topological construct between two adjacent amplifiers (Booster / In-Line-Amplifier ... / Pre-Amplifier) and the Optical Multiplex Section (OMS) MCG, which is the topological relationship between the media port on a filter or coupler where a set of media channels are aggregated and the media port on a filter or coupler where one or more media channel is added to or removed from that aggregate. In this setting, all media channels that are represented by the OMS MCG must be carried over the same serial concatenation of OTS MCGs and amplifiers and a fiber encompasses either an atomic media channel or media channel group, that corresponds to the usable bands in such fiber. When characterizing "C-band only" OMS/OTS, it is commonly assumed a single Media Channel or frequency "range".

2.SDN CONTROL OF MULTI-BAND NETWORKS

A. Software Defined Networking and Model Driven Development

The increased programmability of optical devices, including those being extended to support multi-band transmission and switching, is a key driver for the adoption of SDN in the control and management of optical networks which, along with flexible optical telemetry platforms,

enable more autonomous networks by closing the observe/decide/act loop.

Model driven development (MDD) is an approach to design distributed systems based on the systematic use of data models, which can be automatically processed and validated, used with optimized transfer protocols in such a way that uses cases, business logic and applications can be developed. There are several pillars for MDD: a functional architecture, usually following a client/server approach; transport protocols optimized for the operations of configuration and telemetry such as NETCONF/RESTCONF or gNMI; open and standard data models describing systems and devices and finally a data modeling language to define the data models such as Yang. SDN remains a logically centralized control model architecture, enabling an application layer although as we will see next, the current trend is to decompose into

Fig.2. Control plane architecture involving several dedicated components in a “separation of concerns” disaggregated approach

functional elements or entities and jointly address aspects of i) configuration and control and ii) monitoring and telemetry.

B. Challenges to the SDN control of Multi-Band Networks

As stated, the macroscopic goal is dynamic service provisioning and introducing a certain degree of automation. In this sense, an optical controller is expected to export a standard northbound interface (NBI) that is consumed by applications and, more recently, also by specialized functions deployed in a modular way. Provisioning workflows involve multiple actors and, based on a set of constraints, devices and subsystems are configured following their data models.

The starting initial considerations include: i) to address the additional complexity in network control and management due to the usage of additional optical bands and multiple switching layers; ii) to remove the assumption of quasi uniform behavior for channels and address heterogeneity in devices in terms of capabilities and configurations and iii) to account for physical layer impairments such as stimulated raman scattering or launch power optimization. To meet these objectives, the challenges that an SDN control plane needs to address in this evolution are manifold and they cover:

- i) *architectural aspects*, in which monolithic approaches are being replaced by more modular systems with specialized functions (including, for example, externalized path computation);
- ii) *algorithmic aspects* that are needed to perform resource allocation based on resource allocation and multi-band transmission modelling with QoT validation and,

- iii) *modelling aspects*, to cover the modelling of physical layer impairments, node internal architectures and restrictions (e.g, the existence of per-band demultiplexing) and other applicable concepts

1. Functional Architecture Challenges

A simplistic architecture view of an SDN Control plane (in terms of a single centralized controller on top of an underlying infrastructure and enabling an application ecosystem) is no longer adapted to evolving requirements. Monolithic systems are not flexible and modular enough to support emerging use cases; there is an increasing integration of the packet and optical layers, including pluggable transponders [13] which can be addressed with multiple deployment models.

An SDN control plane requires the coordination (orchestration) of dedicated systems as well as the consolidation of specialized software for aspects such as path computation, path validation or function placement. This is being extended to address the application of Digital Twins [14] for various aspects of network operation as well as the integration of AI/ML assisted operation. For example, as seen in Fig.2, a control plane instance may involve an optical controller that configures the transceivers and which delegates the configuration of the line system to a dedicated (OLS) controller which may, in turn, coordinate with a separate amplifier control. At any level, a controller may rely on external functions. The overall SDN control plane may be containerized and deployed as a service. This evolution towards more “service-based architectures” applying a “separation of concerns” design guideline -- instead of monolithic solutions -- further highlights the need to standard and open interfaces.

This evolution applies not only to configuration and control functions but also to optical monitoring and streaming telemetry with dedicated systems and platforms, (as, shown for example, in a hierarchical setting in Fig.3) which are enablers for advanced algorithms and for closed-loop network automation. While there has been a lot of work related to optical telemetry [15-17], most of it applies to *device telemetry*, in which optical devices (transceivers, amplifiers, ROADMs) act as sources of data. Given the increasing need for telemetry, dedicated platforms are being deployed to assist network operation. Such telemetry platforms can scale to hundreds of data sources, efficiently manage aspects such as time series databases, leverage on architectural options such as message buses or producers/consumers and solve scalability concerns by decoupling the production of telemetry data out of the storage and consumption/visualization of data

Fig.3 Optical Monitoring and Telemetry platform, including SDN control plane acting as both producer/consumer of telemetry data.

Fig4 Common use cases for Controller Telemetry in which an SDN controller or control plane functional element behaves as a data source, sending asynchronous events that can be considered a stream and stored in a time series database.

Given this previously presented functional decomposition of the control plane, the need to state synchronization (e.g., in terms of topology, deployed services, etc.) becomes important. As such, aspects related to *controller telemetry* in which the different components of the control plane become streaming telemetry data sources show increased efficiency compared to methods based on e.g. polling. For example, as seen in Fig.4, there are several use cases benefit from controller telemetry in which state is synchronized such as: i) hierarchical control planes in which parent controllers need an abstracted topology view of child domains ; ii) fault management, where a delegate controller may notify a higher entity of a specific failure or threshold crossing alert, iii) externalized path computation (in which a Path Computation Element or PCE requires an updated traffic engineering database or iv) the usage of DT to keep an updated virtual copy of a physical system.

2. Path Computation and Resource Allocation Challenges

The concepts of path computation, path validation and Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) are often used interchangeably. In the context of this work, the path computation function can be defined as finding a topological path -- as a sequence of links -- and a set of resources to be allocated to support a given connectivity service. In the specific case of the photonic media layer where the main resource is the flexi-grid optical spectrum, the path computation includes assigning the corresponding media channel (group), characterized by its effective frequency slot (nominal central frequency and slot width) and the properties of the corresponding OTSi (group) such as modulation format, or transmission power. This is often referred to as RSA and admits variations depending on the type and terminology of the resources potentially being allocated (optical band, fiber core, or transceiver operational mode) [18]. On the other hand, the path validation function deals with evaluating a path feasibility, e.g., its satisfactory quality of Transmission (QoT) and the impact of the new service on existing services using different techniques such as analytical or simulation models or, more recently AI/ML models. Although these functions are clearly related (and in some cases path validation is part of the computation function) they may be decoupled due to e.g., a formal separation of concerns. Reasons for this include the fact that specialized and externalized software tools may be available (e.g. GNPy [20]) and these may require inventory data and equipment characterization in terms of physical layer that may not be available to the control plane. Variations of this approach exist e.g., the modulation format assignment can be part of the validation process. Finally, let us note that different deployment models apply, including the case where a given path may be pre-computed and pre-validated and provided to the control plane as an additional constraint in the provisioning process.

Path computation and validation are two critical functions, and they are increasingly expected to operate in hybrid mode e.g., as part of planning operations or online, e.g., during the dynamic provisioning of connectivity services. Common approaches range from simple heuristics e.g. based on a combination of Dijkstra/Yen k-shortest paths using a linear multiband transmission modelling accounting for OSNR estimation that depends on reach, amplifier noise figure and fiber attenuation, iterating on the available / feasible bands and using a first-fit approach to more advanced approaches as the one in [19] (see Fig.5) or using well-proven approaches like GNPy [20]. More recently, the usage of Deep/Reinforcement Learning to assist the RSA is gaining attraction [21]. More generic “Digital Twins” may also recommend re-routing actions upon a certain event, such as over-exceeding a defined monitoring threshold, closing the loop where network state, used as input data, is gathered by means of asynchronous streaming telemetry.

Regardless of the path computation function actual implementation, it is a common requirement that the control plane needs to model any required algorithm inputs in an efficient and scalable way. This means that it may not be able to characterize specific parameters of a “per-frequency or per wavelength” basis but work with aggregation, abstraction and simplifications requiring a careful analysis of the underlying trade-off and implications. The amount of modeling data that may be required may have a significant impact in the overall provisioning latency when considering complex workflows that involve multiple control plane entities. To support externalized PCE/DT, the control plane may typically advertise network information related to, as a macroscopic example:

- Network topology, in terms of media channel constructs and OTS, OMS (links), ROADMs & Amplifiers (as network nodes), service endpoints (Tx/Rx pairs, transceivers), supported optical bands and applicable characteristics.
- Capabilities of the deployed transceiver in terms of supported operational modes, frequency ranges, or tunability constraints.
- ROADMs: internal interconnection restrictions
- Characterization of amplifiers’ gains, ripple, operational ranges, Noise Figures, etc.
- Existing services (e.g., OTSi signals)

- Effects (optical impairments) at different stages including fiber linear / non-linear effects, filtering effects, or insertion losses, etc.

Fig.5 Diagram of the interaction between the SDN Controller and the multi-band PCE with macroscopic view of inputs [19].

Algorithms need thus to be carefully stated in terms of their *inputs and outputs* and this should be translated into requirements in the format and semantics of data, as well as on aspects related to how this data is made available to externalized tools. Modelling challenges all relate to providing those inputs while enabling close to optimal solutions.

3. Data Modeling Challenges

Finally, the third key challenge discussed in this paper is related to the actual data modelling, having as a key objective to properly model (i.e., in terms of objects, their attributes and their relationships such as containment of reference) network services, networks topologies, control plane constructs and data plane devices at with different levels of abstraction to enable path computation, QoT validation and performance monitoring, while account for the existence of multiple optical bands (arbitrary frequency ranges). Standard models are key for information exchange and are one of the most active aspects of standardization.

Such modelling work includes, but is not limited to, migrating from “an implicit band” towards a “per band” parameter grouping multiplicity. This means qualifying given data by the band it applies on and a systematic methodology is to revisit existing data models and extend the multiplicity and composition and to parametrize a given aspect with the applicable frequency range.

For example, a basic modelling item relies on the notion of OMS/OTS and how the states on nominal central frequencies within available bands/frequency ranges are encoded, either as port or link attributes. It is, for example, possible to model each OMS MC of the OMS MCG as a distinct entity, enabling finer per-band characterization or, alternatively, to model the whole MCG in a single instance by addressing *different media-channel pools* (see Fig.6). The choice is based, notably, on the heterogeneity of transfer parameters of each band.

Fig.6 GUI of a TAPI-enabled controller showing bands as photonic media network-edge-points (NEP) media channel pools of a single OMS instance,

The former approach is simple and straightforward but fails to capture specific aspects of the band transfer parameters and presents a clear trade-off: wideband transmission modelling may benefit from a finer characterization (e.g., per wavelength) but may not scale or such characterization may not be available. The latter approach multiplies the number of managed entities and instances.

Another recurrent aspect to address scalability relies in the usage of *profiles*, which are groupings of static, invariant data that groups and centralizes related information and that is reused/referred to across several instances avoiding needless duplication but at the same time, is also stored and retrieved as part of the data models to ease information retrieval from a limited number of sources. Specific Standards Defining Organizations (SDOs) or projects are currently defining or augmenting common profiles that cover key aspects of optical networks including fiber profiles, amplification profiles, or transceiver operational profiles. Despite efforts to make profiles common across SDOS they still need to fit in their respective control frameworks and information models, but it should be relatively easy to map information between different profiles. The benefits of using profiles depend on the number of similar instances, but this is often justified.

C. Modelling multiband transmission

To leverage the additional capacity offered by additional optical bands, it is of the essence to model multi-band transmission considering non-negligible frequency dependent parameters. Although the ITU-T has defined the set of optical bands, good design practice should account for a variable number of arbitrary bands – arbitrary frequency ranges – without assumptions of the specific nominal central frequency granularity or slot width granularity. Let us note that, when considering multiband systems, it is often not effective to consider optical fibers as linear media and, in general, fiber nonlinearities need to be addressed during both the design and provisioning phases. In multi-channel systems, in addition to cross-phase modulation (XPM) and four-wave mixing (FWM) nonlinear effects, Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) leads to power transfer from some channels to other channels. Therefore, it is common to adjust the power levels to minimize the effects of nonlinear impairments and their fluctuation as done, for example, in [19]. This explains the need to further develop the modeling of the physical layer and to augment control plane constructs with data models enabling transmission and switching modeling and optical power management. Band specific effects and constrains on the optical signals (also referred to as “media channel transfer parameters”) can be analytically modelled or simulated. This includes, e.g., fibers and

Fig. 9 T-API models for transceiver profiles characterizing transceiver usable operational models

For example, the sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver [30] that is controlled by means of an SDN agent based on extended OpenConfig data models (see Fig10 [31]) can transmit in the S and C bands (work on the L band is ongoing) exports OpenConfig operational mode details that are mapped into TAPI profiles by the SDN controller.

Fig. 10 Optical spectrum of the S-BVT transmitting in the C-band (left) and in the S-band (right), from [31]

D. Switching: ROADM capabilities and impairments.

In many cases, it is often assumed that ROADMs in the optical line system are color-less, direction-less and contention-less (CDC) and enable “any-to-any” cross-connections. In more advanced implementations, a basic description of the internal node is provided, e.g., in terms of a connectivity matrix – that specifies which input degrees are connected to which add/drop stages and/or output degrees. Recently (Fig.11) new data models have been introduced to characterize signal penalties for an aggregated number of cases.

Given the different migration strategies towards multiband networks, it is important to also characterize and represent hardware limitations and architectural restrictions. This also presents a clear trade-off, since optimal solutions may need detailed internal node interconnection, but device models need to scale and control plane instances may be required to support hundreds of nodes and devices.

Despite that current data models allow to characterize internal interconnection and account for basic physical impairment effects by describing a signal degradation for express/add and drop paths, the extension to multi-band networks requires further specifying which bands are supported at each degree and extent connectivity and degradation on a per band basis. In all, from the control plane perspective, actual physical architectures are constrained by the underlying technology (a critical example is that there are no WSS that cover all bands with the same granularity in terms of central frequency

Fig.11. Characterization of the PLI penalties by means of aggregated add, drop or express paths,

and slot width [32]), but, at the same time, device models need to scale for large networks.

D. Amplification and Amplifier Characterization

Fig. 12. Multi-band ROADMs and amplifiers sample physical architectures. Device models can abstract physical details in view of efficiency.

From the point of view of modeling, the characterization of amplifiers relies on a combination of amplification-profiles, that characterize static aspects like gain range, noise figure range, min and max power and gain as well as new attributes and extensions to the OMS CEP(s) entities, with parameters such as actual gain, actual tilt out-VOA or in-VOA. Let us note that these parameters are grouped into lists characterized by the frequency range of application, and it is then possible to have different values for different bands.

However, doped fiber amplifiers that can cover multiple bands are either not technologically mature, do not exist [33], or apply only in

Fig.13. Multi-level networks with single switching nodes (left) and with hybrid / multi-granular nodes. (right).

specific scenarios such as in C+L. The physical architecture of a multiband amplifier may rely on the deployment of one amplifier per band and the usage of DEMUX/MUX stages [34] (Fig.12). In these cases, the characteristic of each band amplifiers may be heterogeneous. It is then a challenge to present the amplifier with an abstracted architecture that does not require the description of internals, either as a topological node or as set of amplification functions with selected operating point characteristics. Initial efforts characterize such amplifiers with a reduced set of parameters as in [35] or [27]. It is expected that refinements on the modelling and characterization of amplifiers will be developed as the technology progresses.

4. MULTI-GRANULAR NODES AND MBoSDM

The steady traffic increase means that solutions based on exploiting additional bands will not suffice in the long term. Further capacity scaling means going parallel and exploiting the spatial dimension [36,37], including the usage of recently developed Sliceable Multidimensional (spectral and spatial) transceivers [38]. In this paper we consider either: i) *single level or flat networks* and ii) *multi-level networks*.

A. Single Level (flat) Networks

In single level or flat optical networks, parallel links are deployed either as bundles of fibers (BoF) or, in a longer term as multi-core fibers with fan-in / fan-out systems. However, such SDM systems are mostly point-to-point and switching only happens at the photonic media / media channel (DWDM) level. In other words, the SDM or spatial layer is systematically terminated at each node and transported OTSi signals are switched (by switching their media channels). ROADMs architectures based on WSS require, in such cases, many ports. A network with max node degree of 9 with bundles of 8 fibers may typically require WSS with ~70 ports (this is without considering add/drop ports). Considering node architectures such as non-spatial lane switching or limiting internal connectivity may reduce the number of required ports at the expense of reduced performance. The introduction of additional bands and the limitations of WSS technology render this problem even more complex.

From the control plane perspective, control functions need to consider internal ROADM connectivity with e.g. WSS modelling e.g. by means of internal links between circuit pack ports, as in OpenROADM device data models [29]. In this sense, this represents a straightforward upgrade, yet the scaling control plane implications means potential scalability issues in the number of controlled entities since there is an N-fold increase in the number of managed links and a subsequent increase in path computation complexity and path computation latency, but overall, the control plane functions remain mostly unmodified.

B. Multi-Level Networks

Multi-Level networks (see Fig.13) extend single level networks by introducing different switching granularities (levels), and these may encompass, for example, WDM switching (media channel switching, either in fixed- flexi- grid); Optical Band Switching (e.g. C-band switching), Waveband switching [39] or Fiber / Core switching. At

Fig.14. Network control and orchestration in SDM and WDM optical networks [40] (top) and the demonstration of SDN-enabled WDM Virtual Network Topologies (VNTs) over SDM networks [41] (bottom)

Fig.15 PoC with a 4 node and 10 MCF links topology shown by the controller (left) and resulting Media channel service between nodes 1 and 2 using optical bypass (core switching). CoreId=1 (red) was allocated by the RSCA algorithm with core continuity constraint

specific points, signals may be switched at a given level/layer. It is known that switching at the highest level (e.g. DWDM switching) yields better performance but introducing switching at the lowest (aggregated) layers may simplify node architectures and be more cost effective.

From the control plane implications, multi-level networks are more complex to manage than single level networks, for the simple fact that the SDN control plane needs to address the additional associated complexity of controlling multiple levels. In this setting node modelling and abstraction are critical aspects to consider and the control plane needs to account for the existence of transitional links (from one client level or layer). SDN control can leverage the previous know-how in terms of control of multilayer networks.

1. Multi-Level Networks with single switching nodes

In this specific case, multi-level networks encompass single switching network elements (nodes with one switching capability or layer). The network can be segmented into what is called “technology domains” or “regions”, with e.g., multi-band DWDM / flexi-grid switching and core/fiber switching, respectively. The control plane implications are addressed by having a hierarchical arrangement of SDN controllers and orchestrators, as is common practice in reference architectures (TAPI, ACTN). In this case, nodes are simpler and technology specific SDN controllers can be deployed. Multiplexing and Demultiplexing connections are commonly coordinated by a parent controller or network orchestrator (see [2]). In [40] (Fig.14) it was shown network orchestration with DWDM services over a Multi-core Fiber (MCF) and in [41] it was extended to cover of Dynamic Deployment of SDN-enabled WDM Virtual Network Topologies (VNTs) over SDM networks.

2. Multi-Level Networks with hybrid (multigranular) nodes

Fig.16. Detail of the considered multi-granular optical nodes showing the configured SDM/CORE service (dotted red), the instantiated MB WDM link (purple) and the flexi-grid 50 GHz media channel service between WXC client ports (dotted grey).

In this, more generic, case network elements are able to terminate data links with different switching capabilities and are characterized by the ability to terminate and/or switch connections at different levels. In the optical domain, such nodes are also referred to as multi-granular nodes. Cases of interest are nodes with dual DWDM (i.e., multiband) over fiber or core (SDM) switching. Such nodes present a classical arrangement with different switching (sub) matrices. Scalability / Efficiency or Feasibility constraints drive multi-stage configurations or hierarchical/coarse/multigranular nodes.

From the control plane perspective, the question to address is what are the extensions (architectural, protocol or algorithmic) required to, potentially jointly, address wavelength (media channel), waveband and SDM switching. With a common deployment model of a single SDN controller per domain, further modeling and standardization work is required to efficiently reuse the model-driven development and existing frameworks for SDN control of MB over SDM networks. In summary, in addition to the previous challenges, the extension to multi-level networks requires:

- Addressing virtual network topologies (VNT) at different levels, the management of logical (virtual) links supported by low layer connections and the overall formal description of additional protocol layers and layer protocol qualifiers (e.g., formally introducing the capability of “core switching” / fiber switching in a standard way).
- Characterize optical links at the SDM layer (e.g., identifying fiber indexes within a bundle of fibers or identifying cores/modes in a multi-core setting).
- Define propagation models and physical impairments extensions to account for aspects such as inter-core cross-talk
- Extend node capability and interconnection models and related abstractions, including transactional links.
- Devise new multi-layer algorithms that enable optical by-pass and grooming with the addition of constraints such as the core-continuity constraint, in which the path computation function and resource allocation must ensure that a given spatial path

uses a single core index, analog to the spectrum continuity constraint of WDM networks.

5. PoC OF A MBoSDM SDN CONTROL PLANE

A. PoC architecture

To illustrate some of the concepts presented in this paper, in this section we detail the proof-of-concept of an SDN control plane for the control of multi-level networks with multi-band enabled flexi-grid networks over SDM (MBoSDM), like the one recently shown in [42]. The SDM layer can be either BoF links with fiber switching or MCF in which the nodes have perform core switching thanks to the usage of Core Selective Switches (CSS) [43].

The network is composed of 4 multi-granular (MBoSDM) nodes (see Fig.15). The optical controller NBI interface, based on the set of Linux Foundation T-API models has been augmented introducing an experimental protocol layer qualifier (PHOTONIC_MEDIA / SDM_CORE). Different entities (NEPs, CEPs) have been augmented to encompass the status of cores/fibers. The user requests a NMC service between client ports and the SDN controller may allocate SDM connections as needed (which involves allocating a single core service between network elements with continuity constraint). In the case shown (Figs. 16 and 17), to support a virtual DWDM flexi-grid link, the SDN controller provisions a connection in the SDM layer (i.e., a core service) using the core c1 that was assigned by the algorithm. Subsequently, such core is marked as in use at both links and cannot be assigned to other connections and a core cross-connection is configured at the intermediate nodes.

1. Path Computation and resource allocation.

Upon request from a NBI client, the path computation algorithm finds a path between two WXC client ports, using, to this end, the set of virtual flexi-grid/MC links (the virtual network topology, VNT). If the algorithm fails, a second step is executed involving finding a core service from the source to the destination node and instantiating a new DWDM virtual link. The controller must deduce the set of usable bands from the

Fig.17. Representation in terms of TAPI Core Information Model

underlying characteristics of the cores / fibers that the service uses. A media channel is then established using the newly allocated link. Virtual links remain instantiated as long as there is at least one client service. In the example, the user requests a 50 GHz NMC service between node_1_port_1 and node_2_port_2. The SDN controller must provision a Core service between nodes (c1) in two links (red dotted connection) which supports the MB link (purple link) on top of which a 50 GHz

2. MBoSDM information models

After the multi-level path has been computed, the SDN controller needs to configure the sub-matrices operations (see Fig.16). The macroscopic operations that the SDN agents at the MBoSDM nodes must support are:

- Setup and release an “add core” from one WXC output port to the CSS of the outgoing degree.
- Setup and release a “express core” connection from one input degree CSS to another output degree CSS.
- Setup and release a “drop core” from the CSS of the input degree to one input port in the WXC.
- Configure connections from WXC client and line ports or between line ports (the latter for switching at the WDM layer and grooming).

Fig.17 shows the representation in terms of TAPI Core Information Model (NEPs/CEPs/Connections); including our proposed extensions for the SDM_CORE switching protocol layer qualifier of the PHOTONIC_MEDIA layer. SDM_CORE NEPs report of the available and allocated core identifiers and SDM_CORE CEPs report on the assigned core. A cross-connection at node 3 enables bypassing media channel (WDM) switching.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The provisioning of network connectivity services needs to be automated via an SDN control plane, using well-established frameworks and platforms. The adoption of MDD, including open and standard interfaces has brought SDN solutions to maturity. That said, in addition to challenges to support the increasing role of network telemetry for autonomous networking, including integration of AI / ML and developments towards more service-based architectures and modular deployments, further research work is required to address optical technologies for sustained capacity scaling such as multi-band systems or SDM. A significant part of the work involves to properly model services, networks, control plane constructs and data plane devices at with different levels of abstraction to enable path computation, QoT validation and performance monitoring while account for the existence of multiple optical bands. There is a trade-off in device modeling, which should remain generic yet account for hardware restrictions.

Current work items in different research communities and SDOs include, but are not limited to, migrating from “an implicit band” towards a “per band” parameter grouping multiplicity.

Overall, extensions to SDN control planes to support multi-band over SDM networks are required to efficiently use the additional capacity, either in single layer or multilayer deployments, and need to address architectural, algorithmic and modelling challenges. Overall, this means a significant increase in complexity, and there is a critical role of standards to ensure interoperability. Generically speaking, standardization of control plane aspects is not fully addressed without a reference and standard data plane. For example, standardization on control of flexi-grid DWDM networks relied on extended ITU-T OTN recommendations defining concepts such as frequency slots, media channels or OTSi. Regarding SDM, to the best of our knowledge,

standardization of control aspects is not addressed by main SDOs at this point, beyond initial proof-of-concept initiatives and research. In some cases (e.g, bundle of fibers) existing standards may be reused (as in fiber switching) but for multicore fibers, data plane aspects such as proper ITU-T layering, fiber core characterization and fiber core switching operations need to be addressed first.

Funding Information. 6G-OPTRAN (references TSI-063000-2021-22, TSI-063000-2021-23, TSI-063000-2021-115), European Commission HE ALLEGRO (101092766), SEASON (101096120) and MICIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 project RELAMPAGO (PID2021-127916OB-I00)

Acknowledgment. This work has received funding from the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program, HE ALLEGRO and SEASON projects. Work partially supported by the RELAMPAGO project (Grant PID2021-127916OB-I00), funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU, the “Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital” and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the framework of the “Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia” and of the “Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia”, project 6G-OPTRAN.

References

1. Telecom Infra Project white paper, “Mandatory Use Cases for SDN Transport (MUST)”, online <https://telecominfraproject.com/oopt/>
2. Ramon Casellas, Ricardo Martínez, Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, Alfredo R. González-Muñiz, Oscar González de Dios, and Juan-Pedro Fernández-Palacios, “Advances in SDN control and telemetry for beyond 100G disaggregated optical networks [Invited]”, *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 14, C23-C37 (2022)
3. R. Casellas; R. Martínez; R. Muñoz; R. Vilalta, “SDN Control of Multi-Band over SDM Optical Networks with Physical Layer Impairments (tutorial)”, OFC2024, San Diego, USA
4. Raul Muñoz, Varsha Lohani, Ramon Casellas, Ricardo Martínez, Ricard Vilalta “Control Of Packet Over Multi-granular Optical Networks Combining Wavelength, Waveband And Spatial Switching For 6G Transport”, OFC2024, Thu.
5. Hoshida, T., Curri, V., Galdino, L., Neilson, D. T., Forsyia, W., Fischer, J. K., Kato, T., and Poggiolini, P., “Ultrawideband systems and networks: Beyond c + l-band,” *Proceedings of the IEEE* 110(11), 1725–1741 (2022).
6. Ruiz, M.; Hernandez, J.A.; Quagliotti, M.; Hugues Salas, E.; Riccardi, E.; Rafel, A.; Velasco, L.; Gonzales De Dios, O. Network Traffic Analysis under Emerging Beyond-5G Scenarios for Multi-Band Optical Technology Adoption. *JOCN* 2023, 15, F36–F47
7. N. Deng, L. Zong, H. Jiang, Y. Duan and K. Zhang, “Challenges and Enabling Technologies for Multi-Band WDM Optical Networks,” in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 3385-3394, 1 June, 2022, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2022.3162725.
8. Napoli, A., Costa, N., Fischer, J. K., ao Pedro, J., Abrate, S., Calabretta, N., Forsyia, W., Pincemin, E., Gimenez, J. P.-P., Matrakidis, C., Roelkens, G., and Curri, V., “Towards multiband optical systems,” in [Advanced Photonics, NeTu3E.1, Optical Society of America (2018).
9. Andrea Sgambelluri et al, “Reliable and Scalable Kafka-based Framework for Optical Network Telemetry”, May 2021 DOI: 10.1364/JOCN.424639
10. ITU-T Rec. G.959.1, “Optical transport network physical layer interfaces”, online <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-G.959.1> 01/24
11. ITU-Rec. G.807 “Generic functional architecture of the optical media network”, inline <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-G.807> 02/20
12. ITU-T Rec. G.698.2, “Amplified multichannel dense wavelength division multiplexing applications with single channel optical interfaces”, online <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-G.698.2> 11/18

13. Alessio Giorgetti, Davide Scano, Andrea Sgambelluri, Francesco Paolucci, Emilio Riccardi, Roberto Morro, Piero Castoldi, and Filippo Cugini, "Enabling hierarchical control of coherent pluggable transceivers in SONiC packet-optical nodes," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 15, 163-173 (2023)
14. Ricard Vilalta, Lluís Gifre, Ramon Casellas, Raul Muñoz, Ricardo Martínez, Alberto Mozo, Antonio Pastor, Diego R. López, Juan Pedro Fernández-Palacios: Applying Digital Twins to Optical Networks with Cloud-Native SDN Controllers. *IEEE Commun. Mag.* 61(12): 128-134 (2023)
15. F. Paolucci, A. Sgambelluri, P. Castoldi, and F. Cugini, "Telemetry Solutions in Disaggregated Optical Networks: an Experimental View," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2021* paper W1G.1.
16. P. González, R. Casellas, J. Pedreno-Manresa, A. Autenrieth, F. Boitier, B. Shariati, J. K. Fischer, M. Ruiz, J. Comellas, and L. Velasco, "Distributed Architecture Supporting Intelligent Optical Measurement Aggregation and Streaming Event Telemetry," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2023*, paper M3Z.4.
17. R. Vilalta, R. Casellas, R. Martínez, R. Muñoz, A. González-Muñiz and J. P. Fernández-Palacios, "Optical Network Telemetry with Streaming Mechanisms using Transport API and Kafka," 2021 European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC), Bordeaux, France, 2021
18. B. Chatterjee, S. Nityananda and E. Oki, "Routing and Spectrum Allocation in Elastic Optical Networks: A Tutorial". *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials.* 17. 1776-1800, 2015
19. E. Kosmatos, R. Casellas, K. Nikolaou, L. Nadal, D. Uzunidis, C. Matrakidis, J. M. Fàbrega, M. Svaluto Moreolo, and A. Stavdas, "SDN-enabled path computation element for autonomous multi-band optical transport networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 15, F48-F62 (2023)
20. A. Ferrari, M. Filer, K. Balasubramanian, Y. Yin, E. Le Rouzic, J. Kundrát, G. Grammel, G. Galimberti, and V. Curri, "GNPy: open source application for physical layer aware open optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 12, C31-C40 (2020).
21. Carlos Hernández-Chulde, Ramon Casellas, Ricardo Martínez, Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, Experimental evaluation of a latency-aware routing and spectrum assignment mechanism based on deep reinforcement learning. *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 15(11): 925-937 (2023)
22. D. Uzunidis, E. Kosmatos, C. Matrakidis, A. Stavdas and A. Lord, "Strategies for Upgrading an Operator's Backbone Network Beyond the C-Band: Towards Multi-Band Optical Networks," in *IEEE Photonics Journal*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1-18, April 2021.
23. D. Uzunidis, K. Nikolaou, C. Matrakidis, A. Stavdas, A. Lord: "Closed-form Expressions for the Impact of Stimulated Raman Scattering Beyond 15 THz", European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2022, Basel, 2022.
24. N. Sambo, A. Ferrari, A. Napoli, N. Costa, J. Pedro, B. Sommerkorn-Krombholz, P. Castoldi, and V. Curri, "Provisioning in multi-band optical networks," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 38, 2598-2605 (2020).
25. Nicola Sambo, Bruno Correia, Antonio Napoli, João Pedro, Leily Kiani, Piero Castoldi, and Vittorio Curri, "Network upgrade exploiting multi band: S- or E-band?," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 14, 749-756 (2022)
26. A. Ferrari, A. Napoli, J. K. Fischer, N. Costa, A. D'Amico, J. Pedro, W. Forysiak, E. Pincemin, A. Lord, A. Stavdas, J. P. F. -P. Gimenez, G. Roelkens, N. Calabretta, S. Abrate, B. Sommerkorn-Krombholz, and V. Curri, "Assessment on the achievable throughput of multiband ITU-TG.652.D fiber transmission systems," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 38, 4279-4291 (2020).
27. A. Mazzini, N. Davis, R. Casellas, editors, "TAPI Reference Implementation Agreement (RIA) v3.1, ONF TR-547 https://github.com/OpenNetworkingFoundation/TAPI/blob/v2.5.0/TR-547-TAPI%20Reference%20Implementation%20Agreement_v3.1.pdf
28. D. Beller, E. Le Rouzic, S. Belotti, G. Galimberti, I. Busy, "A YANG Data Model for Optical Impairment-aware Topology", draft, work in progress, 2024.
29. OpenROADM device data models, online: <http://openroadm.org/overview/>
30. Laia Nadal, Ricardo Martínez, Mumtaz Ali, F. Javier Vilchez, Josep M. Fabrega, Michela Svaluto Moreolo, Ramon Casellas, Advanced optical transceiver and switching solutions for next-generation optical networks. *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 16(8): 64- (2024)
31. Ramon Casellas, Laia Nadal, Ricardo Martínez, Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, Michela Svaluto Moreolo, Photonic device programmability in support of autonomous optical networks. *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 16(8): 53 (2024)
32. Y. Ma et al., "Recent Progress of Wavelength Selective Switch," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 896-903, 15 Feb. 15, 2021, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2020.3022375.
33. Z. Chen et al., "On-Chip Waveguide Amplifiers for Multi-Band Optical Communications: A Review and Challenge," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 3364-3373, 1 June 1, 2022, DOI: 10.1109/JLT.2022.3153447
34. N. Sambo et al., "Network upgrade exploiting multi band: S- or E-band?," in *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 14, no. 9, pp. 749-756, September 2022, doi: 10.1364/JOCN.464386
35. N. Sambo, et al. "Multiband Optical Networks Control and Provisioning", in *proc. of Photonics in Switching Conf (PSC) 2023*.
36. W. Klaus, P. Winzer, K. Nakajima, "The Role of Parallelism in the Evolution of Optical Fiber Communication Systems", *Proceedings of the IEEE.*, 2022.
37. Yutaka Miyamoto and Ryutaro Kawamura, "Space Division Multiplexing Optical Transmission Technology to Support the Evolution of High-capacity Optical Transport Networks," *NTT Technical Review*, Vol. 15, No. 6, June 2017.
38. R. Muñoz, N. Yoshikane, R. Vilalta, J. M. Fàbrega, L. Rodríguez, R. Casellas, M. Svaluto Moreolo, R. Martínez, L. Nadal, D. Soma, Y. Wakayama, S. Beppu, S. Sumita, T. Tsuritani, and I. Morita, "SDN Control of Sliceable Multidimensional (Spectral and Spatial) Transceivers with YANG/NETCONF," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 11, A123-A133 (2019)
39. D. M. Marom et al., "Survey of photonic switching architectures and technologies in support of spatially and spectrally flexible optical networking [invited]," in *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1-26, Jan. 2017.
40. Raul Muñoz, et al. Network control and orchestration in SDM and WDM optical networks (Invited paper). *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC)*, 2020
41. C. Manso, R. Muñoz, F. Balais, R. Casellas, R. Vilalta, R. Martínez, C. Wang, N. Yoshikane, T. Tsuritani, I. Morita, First Demonstration of Dynamic Deployment of SDN-enabled WDM Virtual Network Topologies (VNTs) over SDM networks, *ECOC 2021*
42. Andrea Sgambelluri, Nicola Sambo, Muhammad Ismaeel, Lluís Gifre, Carlos Manso, Michael Enrico, Josep M. Fabrega, Ricard Vilalta, Raul Muñoz, TeraFlowSDN controlling SDM and wideband optical networks. *OFC 2024*: 1-3
43. Y. Kuno, M. Kawasugi, Y. Hotta, R. Otowa, M. Mizoguchi and Y. Sakurai, "Core-Selective Switch for SDM Network based on LCPG and MEMS technology," 2023 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC), San Diego, CA, USA, 2023, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1364/OFC.2023.M4J.4.